

Fearless Innovations in Scholarly Publication in 21st Century

P. S. Aithal¹ & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal^{2*}

¹Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, India

²Faculty, College of Engineering & Technology, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

E-mail : shubhraaithal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The objective of the scholarly publication is the dissemination of newly researched information/knowledge to the general public who have an interest in it for further use. The essential components in the scholarly publication of researched information are systematically written article called scientific article, readers review & suggestions to make the article meaningful, and reachability of published article to the general public of the entire world. As technology and perception of researcher and publisher changes with time and needs, the scholarly research methods, as well as scholarly publication models, are finding new directions. It is noticed that during last few years due to advents in information communication and computation technology (ICCT), the scholarly publication strategy of new knowledge is also changing and many new directions in scholarly research and publication are created by many innovative researchers in order to bring improvements in reachability of publications to every interested reader throughout the world at no cost. Such fearless innovations in the form of new models of scholarly publications are essential and can be adopted using online open publication systems using supporting features of ICCT. This paper identifies such changing objectives of scholarly publications based on changing technology and publication models leads fearless innovations through out-of-the-box thinking. The impact of research repositories, research networks, and digital libraries on research publications are analysed, and their implications on further predictions and suggestions on scholarly publications from both authors and publishers point of views are discussed.

Keywords : New directions in publications, Fearless innovations, Scholarly publications, Authors privilege and rights, Open access publications, Copyright of publications, Citations, Self-publication, Open reviews& feedbacks

1. INTRODUCTION :

Research is a process of developing new knowledge or new interpretation of existing knowledge in an effort of finding truth related to a problem, system, or process. In true sense,

research is a process of fact-finding exercise in the society with an intention to solve the problem, or improve the system, or innovate a process to improve the quality of life. Research is also a process of investigating answers to a question in a scientific and systematic manner by means of the formulation of the hypothesis, data collection on relevant constructs, analysis and interpreting the results in a new way and reaching to the conclusions as a generalized solution [1]. It is well known that scholarly research methods in science and philosophy are changing with time, needs, perception, thinking, and performance. As time progress new research methods may find their importance due to uncovered new problems and availability of more and varied data related to different aspects of the society. Currently, many research methods are used under the umbrella of both qualitative and quantitative research and many new research methods are being added by many researchers at different point of time based on requirement. Along with the addition of such new research methods, scholarly publication strategy of research is also changing with time and the advents of information communication and computation technology (ICCT) has the greatest effect on such changes [2]. The innovations in scholarly publication is essential due to the fact that the conventional publication model has many major drawbacks from researchers point of view which include (1) loss of copyright permanently, (2) delay in publications of important inventions/ research findings, (3) cost involved in publications, (4) the inability of getting sufficient review feedback from the research community belonging to social research media, and (5) Cost and constraints involved in reachability of published full article to the interested readers worldwide. Many new directions in scholarly research and publication are created by many innovative researchers in order to bring improvements in both qualities of research and world reachability of publications to every interested reader at no cost [3]. Such fearless innovations in the form of new models of scholarly research and publications will further boost the confidence and give inspirations and courage to create new publication models to make their publications ubiquitous using technology and decreases hesitations to use such new avenues of scholarly publication models. The paper focuses on the critical analysis of the drawbacks of existing scholarly publication models and some of the possible new directions in scholarly publications for 21st century including the importance of innovations in scholarly publications suitable to lead progress in the field. The paper also identifies changing objectives of scholarly publications based on changing technology and publication models based on fearless innovations through out-of-the-box thinking. The impact of research repositories, research networks, and digital libraries on research publications are analysed, and their implications on further predictions and suggestions on scholarly publications from both authors and publishers point of views are discussed.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

The study is a conceptual observation and focuses on the critical analysis of existing/conventional scholarly publication models and their drawbacks from authors/researchers point of view, and some of the possible new directions in scholarly publications for the 21st century. The objective of this study include but not limited to :

- (1) To analyse conventional scholarly publication models and their drawbacks from authors/researchers point of view.
- (2) To discuss the importance of innovations in scholarly publications in the 21st century.
- (3) To identify and analyse some of the important new scholarly publication models which can contribute substantially to knowledge dissemination.
- (4) To identify changing objectives of scholarly publications based on changing technology and publication models based on fearless innovations through out-of-the-box thinking.

(5) To study the impact of research repositories, research networks, and digital libraries on research publications.

3. CONVENTIONAL SCHOLARLY PUBLICATION MODELS AND THEIR DRAWBACKS :

The conventional scholarly publication model consists of identifying an international publisher who has access to supply the journal issues to many libraries of many countries all over the world through their strong library networks. In order to publish an article in such journals, the author has to transfer the copyright of the article in Publishers name, wait for completion of review and print for publication in the form of books and their availability in libraries for the public. Consequently, some of the international publishers could become popular due to their capability of commanding subscription to more number of libraries. Such international publishers started to command the scholarly publication model as publisher friendly rather than researcher/author friendly. As a result, the researchers/authors who have published their research papers with such publishers have lost their copyright and entire control on their articles. Such conventional scholarly publication model has many drawbacks from the researchers point of view as listed below :

(1) Loss of copyright permanently : Copyright is considered as intellectual property issue and the author should have copyright of his article which is the outcome of his research contribution. It is now argued that as per changing perception and opportunity of using ICCT, the author should have copyright with him and he should able to distribute his inventions to the public by allowing it to read/download from his website. Holding copyright in authors name is also essential to apply patent for such inventions in future days. It is also argued that the patent review normally takes a long time before sectioning so that it is a smart decision to publish the invention by keeping the copyright of such scholarly publication with authors. But the conventional model of scholarly publication involves the transfer of copyright of the article to the publisher who sells the article forever without any revenue share with the researcher. Naturally this model of transfer of copyright completely forever is not acceptable to the researcher/authors and hence alternative publication model to overcome copyright issue and to retain it in researchers/authors name is essential.

(2) Delay in publications of important inventions/ research findings :

The conventional publication model using top international publishers usually takes years together for final publication after submission of the paper. This time gap is due to the continuous improvement of the paper and its abstract in the name of reviews with the intension to convert it into sellable paper so that the publisher can earn more. This process of converting the abstract of the paper more attractive without leaking any results to increase the curiosity of the reader and business value of the paper consumes long time without adding any value to it. This process of converting a research paper into sellable paper by publishers increases the time gap between the first submission and final publication to several months and hence unnecessary delay in publication.

(3) Cost involved in publications :

Many publishers impose submission charges and article processing charges to the articles to be submitted for publications apart from the compulsory transfer of copyright. These article submission charges and article processing charges are additional expenditure for the researchers apart from their research expenditure. This leads to the authors' intention to find an alternative way of publication.

(4) Inability of getting sufficient review feedback from the research community belonging to social research media :

The review of research articles submitted to international publishers takes a long time even though one or two reviews are undertaken. Since international publishers are not paying any review fee to the reviewers, many papers sent for review will be rejected for review by potential reviewers due to their busy time schedules. To avoid this problem, international publishers appoint permanent reviewers cannot review the contents of the papers but helps to convert the saleable value by redesigning the abstract in an attractive way. This process even though time consuming, will not provide any useful suggestions to improve the real value of the paper. Alternatively, if the researcher posts the paper in different social research media, many related researchers give their valuable suggestions to improve the quality of the paper. Thus the review process carried by conventional international publishers has no value except adding a delay in publication to researchers.

(5) Cost and Constraints in reachability of published full article to the interested readers worldwide :

After transferring the copyright, the researcher loses the control on the paper and he cannot distribute the published paper to the general public either free or selling at a price which hinders the reachability of his full paper to many interested researchers in that or related fields.

(6) Low citations due to non-open access nature of the published articles :

The citation is one of the important parameters to measure the success of a research findings and publication. It represents the continuation of research on that topic either by same research group (self-citation) or other research groups worldwide (external citation) [4, 5]. If the published research paper is not openly accessible or not available for search results, then such papers will not get citations oftenly.

4. NEW SCHOLARLY RESEARCH MODELS :

There are many methodologies and methods used in scholarly research in both natural sciences and philosophical sciences. These methodologies and methods lead to many models in scholarly research.

Table 1 : Some of the Qualitative Research Methods & Models used in this century

S. No.	Qualitative Research Methods	Objective	Procedure
1	Observation Method	Observation of the system and its environment	Data collection via observation
2	Content Analysis	Investigating a report systematically	Structured and systematic
3	Focus Group Method	Collection of information from group	Analysing the information from focus groups
4	Personal Interview	Opinion/experience Collection	May be unstructured, semi-structured and structured

	method		
5	Projective techniques	Idea of projecting one-self or feelings on ambiguous objects	Indirect questioning
6	Socio-metric analysis	Analysing information obtained from different groups	Involves measuring the choice, communication and interpersonal relations of people in different groups
7	Industry Analysis	Analysing certain issues of an industry	Use suitable analysing framework
8	Company / NGO Analysis	Analysing certain issues of a company or an NGO	Use suitable analysing framework
9	Patent Analysis	Analysing a patent granted on a new product or new process or new system	Use of suitable framework to analyse technology/ process
10	Ideal System based Model Analysis	Identifying the research gap by comparing present characteristics and ideal characteristics of a system	Use of developing Ideal system model and its characteristics by classifying them as input, process, output, and environmental characteristics
11	Accountability Model	Optimizing the organizational human elements performance	Continuously improving the performance using the eight elements of Theory of Accountability

5. CHANGING OBJECTIVES OF SCHOLARLY PUBLICATIONS :

Scholarly publishing authors are literary highjacked by Top publishers all over the world. In the name of Journal impact factor and universal reachability through large library networks or large number of library subscriptions, these so-called top publishers are looting the rights of authors. Through lobbying they create artificial barriers to new journals mainly in developing countries by bribing the decision makers and government agencies to develop policies in their favour. For their profit and maintain monopoly they follow black ocean strategy.

(1) Through copyright transfer during publication, the authors literary lose their control on their own research and findings. These publishers in the name of peer review process, converts the paper into sellable stuff for higher price by asking the modifications in the abstracts of the papers to an attractive manner. This will enhance the sellability of papers for high price. Many authors who publish their papers in so called top ranked journals in some cases have to pay Paper Submission Charge (PSC) in terms of several hundred dollars. The submitted paper is reviewed in such a way that only the format of the papers are made to change to sell it at higher prize without modifying the technical or new knowledge part of the paper. This process of review consumes six months to one year so that the paper will be acceptable for publication most of the time after one year of submission and it will take further waiting time for actual publication and to dispatch to the Libraries. Due to such time gap, the contents of scholarly publication become obsolete before reaching the readers hand.

(2) Lobbying against Open Access.

(3) Lobbying against Fair Publication Policies in Many Countries.

(4) Action against Authors posting their own articles in their own blog.

(5) Constraints on applying patents on authors of their own published papers.

(6) Restriction on uploading published papers on Research Networks.

Table 2 : List of Big five for-profit global publishers

S. No.	Journal Publisher	No. of Journals	Paper purchase price/Article	Article Processing Charge for Open Access Publication
1	ElsevierJournals	3,300	\$ 50	\$ 3,000 (Average)
2	Springer	2,900	\$ 40	\$ 3,000 (Average)
3	Wiley-Blackwell	2,400	\$ 38	\$ 800 to \$ 4,500
4	Taylor & Francis	2,150	\$ 50	\$ 2,950
5	SagePublications	1,300	\$ 36	\$ 700 to \$ 3,000

It is known that five for-profit companies (Elsevier, Springer Science+Business Media, Wiley-Blackwell, Taylor & Francis, and Sage) accounted for 50% of articles published in 2013 [6, 7].

Elsevier is an information and analytics company and one of the world's major providers of scientific, technical, and medical information. It was established in 1880 as a publishing company. It is a part of the RELX Group, known until 2015 as Reed Elsevier. Its products include journals such as *The Lancet* and *Cell*, the ScienceDirect collection of electronic journals, the *Trends* and *Current Opinion* series of journals, the online citation database Scopus, and the [Clinical-Key](#) solution for clinicians. Elsevier's products and services include the entire academic research lifecycle, including software and data-management, instruction and assessment tools [8]. Elsevier publishes more than 430,000 articles annually in 2,500 journals. Its archives contain over 13 million documents and 30,000 e-books. Total yearly downloads amount to more than 900 million. Elsevier's high profit margins (37% in 2017) and its copyright practices have subjected it to criticism by researchers.

Table 2 : List of Countries who have taken initiation to ban for-profit publishers for scholarly publications/ library subscription

S. No.	Country	Name of the Publishers	Reason	Reference
1	Finland	Elsevier	High Journal Subscription fee	[9]
2	Germany	Elsevier	Closed Access policy	[9]
3	Netherlands	Elsevier	Closed Access policy	[9]
4	South Korea	3 Top Publishers	High Journal Subscription fee	[9]
5	Sweden	Elsevier	Closed Access policy & High Journal Subscription fee	[9]
6	Taiwan	Elsevier	High Journal Subscription fee	[9]
7	USA (Some	Top Publishers	High Journal	[9]

	Universities only)		Subscription fee	
--	--------------------	--	------------------	--

6. INNOVATIONS IN SCHOLARLY PUBLICATIONS IN 21ST CENTURY :

6.1 Open Access Publications :

Creative Commons Publications which are open access for both readers and authors. Authors can upload the paper in any open access websites like social research consortiums.

6.2 Open Access Publications by Institutions :

Many institutions and universities are really visionaries in this regard and involved in not for profit model of journal publications. Based on charitable organizations support, they are publishing peer reviewed journals for open access without article processing charges to the authors. Such organizations which do not charge article processing fee for the authors for their open access publication carry out the peer review systematically in a reasonable time for online publications. This decreases the time gap between paper submission and online paper publication and hence supports speedy publication. When peer reviewed scholarly publication becomes a service rather than a business, so called Predatory journals will disappear from the market.

6.3 Other Innovations : Other innovations like Self Publications by Individuals, Plagiarism, Peer Review, Citations, Self Citation, Publishers Strategy, Journal Impact Factor and its Consequence on Authors Decision etc. are also seen recently in scholarly publications.

7. CONCLUSION :

The essential components in the scholarly publication of researched information are systematically written article called scientific article, readers review & suggestions to make the article meaningful, and reachability of published article to the general public of the entire world. As technology and perception of researcher and publisher changes with time and needs, the scholarly research methods, as well as scholarly publication models, are finding new directions. It is noticed that during last few years due to advents in information communication and computation technology (ICCT), the scholarly publication strategy of new knowledge is also changing and many new directions in scholarly research and publication are created by many innovative researchers in order to bring improvements in reachability of publications to every interested reader throughout the world at no cost. Such fearless innovations in the form of new models of scholarly publications are essential and can be adopted using online open publication systems using supporting features of ICCT. This paper identifies such changing objectives of scholarly publications based on changing technology and publication models leads fearless innovations through out-of-the-box thinking. The impact of research repositories, research networks, and digital libraries on research publications are analysed, and their implications on further predictions and suggestions on scholarly publications from both authors and publishers point of views are discussed.

REFERENCES :

[1] Aithal, P. S. (2017). Comparative Study of Various Research Indices used to measure quality of Research Publications. *International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research (IJAASR)*, 2(1), 81-89. DOI :<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.569763>.

- [2] Aithal, P. S.,(2017). Company Analysis – The Beginning Step for Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 1(1), 1-18. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.573769>.
- [3] Aithal, P. S. (2017). Industry Analysis – The First Step in Business Management Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1), 1-13. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.810347>.
- [4] Aithal, P. S., Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2017). Ideal Analysis for Decision Making in Critical Situations through Six Thinking Hats Method. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 1(2), 1-9. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.838378>.
- [5] Aithal, P. S. (2017). ABCD Analysis of Recently Announced New Research Indices. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 1(1), 65-76. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.583644>.
- [6] Buranyi, Stephen (27 June 2017). "Is the staggeringly profitable business of scientific publishing bad for science?". *The Guardian*. Retrieved 1 November 2018.
- [7] "Time to break academic publishing's stranglehold on research". *New Scientist*. 21 November 2018. Retrieved 27 November 2018.
- [8] Buranyi, Stephen (2017-06-27). "Is the staggeringly profitable business of scientific publishing bad for science?". *The Guardian*. ISSN [0261-3077](https://doi.org/10.1017/S02613077). Retrieved on 2017-07-02.
- [9] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Elsevier>